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Review Article

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN TYPE 1 DIABETES AND AUTOIMMUNE THYROID DISEASE: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract:

Background: Type 1 diabetes (T1D) is an autoimmune disease affecting insulin production. Individuals with T1D are known to have an increased risk of developing other autoimmune conditions, with autoimmune thyroid disease (AITD) being the most common. **Objectives:** To evaluate the current literature on the association between T1D and AITD. **Methods:** A thorough electronic search of relevant databases was implemented to identify studies that met the inclusion criteria. An extensive search of PubMed, SCOPUS, Science Direct, and Web of Science was performed to locate relevant material. **Results:** Our data includes eleven trials with 21,812 participants and 11744 (53.2%) were males. The prevalence of AITD ranged from 9.2% to 75% with a total prevalence of 4425 (20.3%). Age, a long disease duration, and female gender are associated with an increased frequency of AITD in the population with T1D. Early glycemic control is recommended since the main consequences of diabetes are chronicity and inadequate glycemic control. The presence of diabetic ketoacidosis at the time of diagnosis, age less than five years at T1D diagnosis, and a major autoimmune history in the family were all predictive factors for multiple autoimmunity. **Conclusion:** There is a well-established correlation between AITD and T1D since both disorders often co-occur because of similar immune and genetic mechanisms. AITD, which includes diseases like Graves' disease and Hashimoto's thyroiditis, is more common in patients with T1D. Common autoimmune mechanisms, in which the immune system unintentionally targets the body's own tissues, are thought to be the cause of this relationship. In order to maximize patient care and avoid complications, it is essential to identify and treat AITD in patients with T1D.

Keywords: Type 1 diabetes, autoimmune thyroid disease, prevalence, incidence, Systematic review.

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INTRODUCTION:

T1D and AITD are two different autoimmune disorders that often occur together in the same individual. This can complicate the management of both conditions and lead to additional health risks [1]. In T1D, the immune system targets and kills the pancreatic cells that produce insulin. As a result, there is less insulin produced, which is required to control blood sugar levels. T1D symptoms include excessive thirst, intense hunger, frequent urination, exhaustion, and blurred vision. Serious side effects include heart disease, renal failure, and nerve damage that can result from untreated T1D [2].

In contrast, AITD is a collection of illnesses where the thyroid gland is attacked by the immune system, resulting in inflammation and destruction. Graves' illness and Hashimoto's thyroiditis are the two most prevalent types of AITD. Depending on the particular disease, AITD symptoms might vary, but frequent ones include fatigue, changes in heart rate, weight gain or loss, hair loss, and sensitivity to heat or cold [3]. The link between T1D and AITD lies in their shared autoimmune nature. Both conditions result from an abnormal immune response that mistakenly targets the body's own tissues. Though the precise causes of this correlation are unclear, it is thought that people with one autoimmune disease are more likely to develop another. Autoimmune illnesses may arise as a result of hormone imbalances, environmental stimuli, or genetic causes [4].

Diagnosing T1D and AITD typically involves a combination of blood tests and physical exams. For T1D, a blood test measuring blood sugar levels and insulin levels can confirm the diagnosis [5]. Blood tests that assess thyroid hormone and antibody levels are typically used to diagnose AITD. The thyroid gland's anatomy can also be evaluated using imaging techniques like ultrasonography [6].

Insulin pumps or daily insulin injections are used in T1D treatment to regulate blood sugar levels. Other crucial elements of managing type 1 diabetes include frequent physical activity, eating a nutritious diet, and monitoring blood sugar levels. For AITD, treatment

may include thyroid hormone replacement therapy, anti-inflammatory medications, or surgery to remove part of the thyroid gland. Monitoring thyroid function through blood tests is essential to ensure that hormone levels are within a normal range [7].

Managing both T1D and AITD can be challenging, as the two conditions may interact and affect each other. For example, fluctuations in blood sugar levels can impact thyroid function, and changes in thyroid hormone levels can affect blood sugar regulation [8].

This study investigates the co-occurrence of two common autoimmune diseases: T1D and AITD. Understanding this association can improve diagnosis, and treatment strategies, and potentially identify shared genetic or environmental factors. Patients with T1D are at an increased risk of developing other autoimmune diseases, particularly AITD. The exact prevalence and factors influencing this association are not fully understood.

Study Objectives:

- To assess the pooled prevalence of AITD in patients with T1D.
- To assess the type distribution of AITD within the T1D population.
- To explore potential factors affecting the co-occurrence of these diseases.

Methods

We implemented this systematic review in line with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) [9] criteria. An internet-based search was performed on PubMed, Web of Science, SCOPUS, and Science Direct to find English-language studies on the connection between T1D and AITD. Relevant keywords were used in the search method in these scenarios. Two reviewers separately searched through the search outcomes, chose relevant papers, collected data, and utilized the appropriate assessment procedures to establish how strong the included study was. These reviewers

independently extracted essential data and critically appraised the quality of included research using established evaluation tools, ensuring the inclusion of high-quality studies and reliable data for subsequent analysis and synthesis in this systematic review.

Eligibility Criteria:

Inclusion criteria:

1. Studies that investigate the association between T1D and AITD.
2. Research that is printed in publications with peer review.
3. Studies published within the last five years (2020-2024).
4. Studies available in the English language.
5. Research conducted on human subjects.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Studies that do not focus on the association between T1D and AITD.
2. Studies not available in the English language.
3. Animal or in vitro studies.
4. Reviews, case reports, editorials, and opinion pieces.

Data Extraction

Rayyan (QCRI) was utilized to check the search results and ensure accuracy [10]. The inclusion and exclusion criteria were employed to establish the relevance of the search results titles and abstracts. The study team thoroughly reviewed papers that met the inclusion criteria. Consensus was employed to resolve disputes. Key study data were recorded using an established data extraction form, including titles, authors, publication year, study location, gender distribution, participant demographics, AITD prevalence, thyroid condition, T1D duration, and primary outcomes. To investigate the probability of bias, a neutral evaluation instrument was developed.

Strategy for Data Synthesis

Using information from relevant studies, descriptions of the research findings and features were produced in order to offer a qualitative assessment. Following the completion of data collection for the systematic review, the most effective way to ensure the utilization of the data from the included studies was determined.

Risk of Bias Assessment

The Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) [11] critical assessment criteria designed for studies reporting prevalence data will be applied to evaluate the quality of the research included in this investigation. Nine questions make up this tool, and the answers are ranked as either positive (rated as 1) or negative (scoring as 0), unclear, or irrelevant. Based on total ratings that fall below 4, between 5 and 7, and above 8, studies will be categorized as poor, moderate, or high quality, respectively. Researchers will independently assess the quality of the studies they undertake, and any disagreements in the evaluations will be settled by cooperative discussion to guarantee agreement and precision in the quality assessment procedure.

RESULTS:

Systematic search outcomes

Following the removal of 898 duplicates, a systematic search yielded 1802 study papers. After 904 studies' titles and abstracts were reviewed, 788 papers were rejected. Out of the 116 reports that needed to be obtained, 6 articles were not found. 110 articles passed the full-text screening procedure; 81 were dismissed because the study results were erroneous, 14 because the population type was incorrect, 2 were editor's letters, and 2 were abstracts. The eligibility requirements were satisfied by eleven research publications that have been incorporated in this systematic review.

Figure 1 depicts an overview of the approach used to choose the research.

Figure 1: A PRISMA diagram is used to summarize the study decisions.

Sociodemographics of the comprised participants and studies

Table 1 displays the sociodemographic information from the research articles. Our data includes eleven trials with 21,812 participants and 11744 (53.2%) were males. Seven studies were cross-sectional [12-16, 18, 20], three were retrospective cohorts [17, 21, 22], and one was a prospective observational study [17]. Two studies were conducted in Saudi Arabia [12, 16], two in Spain [18, 20], one in Brazil [13], one in Syria [14], one in Taiwan [15], one in Turkey [17], one in Greece [19], one in Poland [21], and one in the UK [22].

Clinical outcomes

The clinical data are presented in **Table (2)**. Seven studies investigated the incidence of AITD among T1D patients [14-17, 20, 22], two investigated hypothyroidisms [12, 13], and two investigated Hashimoto's thyroiditis [19, 21]. The prevalence of AITD ranged from 9.2% [14] to 75% [13] with a total prevalence of 4425 (20.3%). Age [15, 16], a longer disease duration [14, 15], and female sex [15, 18] are associated with an increased frequency of AITD in the population with T1D. Early glycemic control is recommended since the main consequences of diabetes are chronicity and inadequate glycemic control [12]. Predictive factors for multiple autoimmunity included having diabetic ketoacidosis at diagnosis, being younger than five years old when diagnosed with T1D, and having a significant autoimmune history in the family [19].

Table 1: Sociodemographic parameters of the involved populations.

Study	Study design	Country	Participants	Mean age	Males (%)
Albrahim et al., 2022 [12]	Cross-sectional	Saudi Arabia	251	26.3 ± 7.7	103 (41%)
Gomes et al., 2024 [13]	Cross-sectional	Brazil	1,760	30.2 ± 11	991 (56.3%)
Hazzaa et al., 2024 [14]	Cross-sectional	Syria	76	15.6 ± 5.3	64 (81.2%)
Wang et al., 2023 [15]	Cross-sectional	Taiwan	761	17.8 ± 8.5	364 (47.8%)
Mohammed et al., 2023 [16]	Cross-sectional	Saudi Arabia	2258	12 - 56	909 (40.3%)
Korkmaz et al., 2023 [17]	Prospective observational	Turkey	96	10 - 20	27 (33.3%)
Herranz-Antolín et al., 2022 [18]	Cross-sectional	Spain	2586	39.4 ± 13.5	1309 (50.6%)
Kakleas et al., 2022 [19]	Retrospective cohort	Greece	121	11.9 ± 4.6	63 (52.1%)
Gimenez-Perez et al., 2022 [20]	Cross-sectional	Spain	13,571	45.2 ± 15.3	7745 (57%)
Szcześniak et al., 2021 [21]	Retrospective cohort	Poland	188	42.1 ± 15	94 (50%)
Kakleas et al., 2021 [22]	Retrospective cohort	UK	144	12.5 ± 5	75 (52.1%)

Table (2): Clinical parameters and outcomes of the comprised research.

Study ID	Thyroid condition	Prevalence of AITD	Diabetes duration	Main outcomes	JBI
Alibrahim et al., 2022 [12]	Hypothyroidism	41 (16.3%)	12.2 ± 7.6	The frequency of autoimmuneism was comparable in Saudi persons with T1D across genders and age groups, showing little to no variation. The prevalence of autoimmunity's clinical symptoms was higher in women. Early glycemic control is recommended since the main consequences of diabetes were chronicity and inadequate glycemic control.	Moderate
Gomes et al., 2024 [13]	Hypothyroidism	258 (75%)	15.5 ± 9.3	The majority of individuals had AITD, with hypothyroidism being the most common change.	Moderate
Hazzaa et al., 2024 [14]	AITD	7 (9.2%)	5.77 ± 4.58	Due to the higher prevalence of anti-TPO Ab in older patients and those with longer durations of diabetes, regular monitoring is required. Furthermore, it is advised that all T1D patients, especially female patients, have regular annual monitoring by US and anti-TPO Ab to detect AITDs.	Moderate
Wang et al., 2023 [15]	AITD	197 (25.9%)	15.5 ± 8	In the pediatric T1D population, AITD is more common in those who are older, have a prolonged disease duration, and are female. To identify AITD in children and adolescents with T1D as soon as possible, a yearly screening program should be implemented.	Moderate
Mohammed et al., 2023 [16]	AITD	429 (18.9%)	6 ± 1.5	Autoimmune disorders and autoimmune thyroiditis are frequently seen in young individuals with T1D diagnoses. AI and polyglandular autoimmune disorders are frequently seen in older T1D patients.	High
Korkmaz et al., 2023 [17]	AITD	32 (33.3%)	15.6	Children without clinically discernible diabetic retinopathy who have co-occurring AITD and T1D experience reduced retinal microcirculation, just like children with T1D who are matched in terms of age, race, sex, blood pressure, and plasma lipid levels.	Moderate

Herranz-Antolín et al., 2022 [18]	AITD	879 (34%)	19.4 ± 10.6	The existence of T1D diabetes and the female gender were the characteristics that were independently linked to the occurrence of ATD.	Moderate
Kakleas et al., 2022 [19]	Hashimoto thyroiditis	30 (25.2%)	2 months to 14.5 years	Within the pediatric T1D population, AITD is more prevalent in older, female patients with a longer disease duration. In order to promptly detect AITD in children and adolescents with T1D, a yearly screening program had to be instituted.	Moderate
Gimenez-Perez et al., 2022 [20]	AITD	2,485 (18.3%)	NM	Concurrent AITD is associated with a lower prevalence of peripheral artery disease and renal disease, but the presence of other AITDs is associated with the development of T1D.	High
Szcześniak et al., 2021 [21]	Hashimoto thyroiditis	43 (23%)	16.8 ± 10.3	The degree to which diabetes is controlled and the emergence of its complications are not substantially impacted by the coexistence of Hashimoto's thyroiditis. In patients with this thyroid illness, autonomic neuropathy only rarely manifests as an impaired sense of hyperglycemia.	Moderate
Kakleas et al., 2021 [22]	AITD	24 (16.7%)	1.6-7.2	In children with T1D, the degree of acidity at diagnosis is highly correlated with the emergence of related autoimmune disorders and may serve as a predictor for the development of numerous autoimmune diseases.	Moderate

*NM=Not-mentioned

DISCUSSION:

This systematic review included recent updates about the relationship between AITD and T1D. We found that the prevalence of AITD ranged from 9.2% [14] to 75% [13] with a total prevalence of 4425 (20.3%). The most common AITDs, coexisting in 17–30% of patients, are AITD and T1DM [23]. They may present clinically as hyperthyroidism or hypothyroidism [24].

Dysfunctional auto-antigen surveillance and autoreactive immune responses by T, B, macrophage, and dendritic cells are the hallmarks of AITD. These reactions lead to the generation of particular autoantibodies against thyroglobulin (TGA) and thyroid peroxidase (TPOAb) [25]. Approximately 25% of pediatric patients with T1DM already exhibit a positive titre of antithyroid antibodies at the time of diagnosis [26].

Symptomatic hypothyroidism may not significantly impair diabetes control, in accordance with the International Society for Pediatric and Adolescent Diabetes (ISPAD) Guidelines [27], and there have been no statistically significant changes in HbA1c between T1D that is isolated and T1D that coexist with AITD [28].

We discovered that in the T1D population, there is a higher prevalence of AITD in those who are older [15, 16], have a longer disease duration [14, 15], and are female [15, 18]. Significant progress has been made in the last 20 years on the mechanisms behind the development of AITD, according to a thorough investigation. It is widely accepted that a complex interaction between genetic susceptibility, environmental hazards, and several epigenetic

variables influences the pathophysiology of AITD [29, 30]. Genetic factors are the most common factor contributing 70–80% of the risk of developing thyroid autoimmunity, according to twin/family studies. Environmental factors contribute to the remaining 20–30% [31].

Subsequent investigations ought to concentrate on clarifying the genetic and molecular pathways that connect AITD and T1D. Comprehending these pathways may facilitate the creation of focused treatments and prophylactic measures. Large-scale longitudinal studies are also required to determine risk factors for the development of AITD in individuals with T1D and to gain a better understanding of the natural history of these co-occurring diseases.

In order to guarantee early detection and treatment, clinical practice should place a strong emphasis on the significance of routine screening for thyroid dysfunction in patients with T1D. Personalized medicine techniques and genetic screening could be combined to improve the way certain autoimmune diseases are treated. Additionally, patient education and support initiatives can enhance patients with both T1D and AITD's overall quality of life and adherence to treatment regimens.

CONCLUSION:

There is a well-established correlation between AITD and T1D, since both disorders often co-occur because of similar immune and genetic mechanisms. AITD, which includes diseases like Graves' disease and Hashimoto's thyroiditis, is more common in patients with T1D. Common autoimmune mechanisms, in which the immune system unintentionally targets the body's own tissues, are thought to be the cause of this relationship. In order to maximize patient care and avoid complications, it is essential to identify and treat AITD in patients with T1D.

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